

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

INTERPRETATION OF THE PROCESS OF MASTERING "THEORETICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL BASES OF SOLVING THE SYSTEM OF LINEAR ALGEBRAIC EQUATIONS" IN THE TEACHING OF "ALGEBRA"

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ABSTRACT

In the article, it is emphasized that systems with an arbitrary number of equations and an arbitrary number of unknowns are studied in "Algebra", which has a special place among the compulsory subjects of the "Mathematics teaching" specialty in pedagogically oriented higher schools, and attention is directed to the possible forms of the System of Linear Algebraic Equations (SLAE). The concepts of "equivalence" and "elementary transformation" are explained by noting the important role of the concept of equivalence and equivalence of the system of equations in the study of the system of equations.

Here, the complete study of a system of linear algebraic equations is "determining whether the given system has a solution, i.e. first, whether it is a joint system", "determining whether it has a unique or multiple solutions", "if the system is joint, finding all its solutions", it is shown that it contains ingredients such as. Also comments on the role of the Gauss method, Kramer's rule, Kronecker-Capelli criterion, advantages and disadvantages in studying and mastering the solution of SLAE are given.

The article shows that a special "categorical apparatus" conditions the process of studying the SLAE. At what level the student has mastered the essence and functions of the concepts included in these mentioned forms of spiritual education – "enabling features", he becomes the subject of solving skills of SLAE in an adequate way.

Keywords: matrices and their different types, determinant and its types, methods of calculating determinants, main determinant (determinant of the system), auxiliary determinant, minor and algebraic complement (adjunct), operations on determinants and matrices, rank, rank of a matrix, methods of calculating the rank of matrices, extended the matrix.

Relevance of the research topic. It is not difficult to see from the research on scientific sources that there have been many studies on the philosophy, didactics, and implementation technology of teaching all the subjects taught in general education schools, but in pedagogically oriented higher schools, there are no complete or separate topics and research on the teaching of concepts is non-existent. The mentioned "theoretical gap" has a negative effect on the teaching process of these subjects and its level of efficiency. Therefore, we claim the relevance of developing the "interpretation of the process of mastering the theoretical and technological bases of solving the system of linear algebraic equations" in the teaching of the subject "Algebra".

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials. It is known that systems with an arbitrary number of equations and an arbitrary number of unknowns are studied in "Algebra", which has a special place among the compulsory subjects of the "Mathematics teaching" specialty. So, it is not necessary that the number of equations and the number of unknowns in the systems are the same.

A system of n -unknown m -number linear algebraic equations whose coefficients are from the field P

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = b_2 \\ \text{-----} \\ a_{m1}x_1 + a_{m2}x_2 + \dots + a_{mn}x_n = b_m \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

(where $m, n \in N, a_{ij}, b_{ij} \in P$) is called the system of the figure. Here $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ are called unknowns, a_{ij} ($i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n}$) coefficients, and $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m$ free limits. In the system we are looking at, of equation i , $1 \leq i \leq m$, the writing form $a_{i1}x_1 + a_{i2}x_2 + \dots + a_{in}x_n = b_i$ of the i -th equation, ($a_{ij} \rightarrow$ is the coefficient of the variable in the i -th equation, b_i – is the free limit of the i -th equation) or in short as $\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}x_j = b_i$ (where $i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n}$).

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = 0 \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = 0 \\ \text{-----} \\ a_{m1}x_1 + a_{m2}x_2 + \dots + a_{mn}x_n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

system (2) is called a (derived or associative) homogeneous system of system (1).

According to the appearance of the given system, they distinguish its so-called "rectangular", "square", "triangular", "trapezoidal" types. In other words, when s and n for arbitrary positive integers $s < n$.

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a'_{22}x_2 + a'_{23}x_3 + \dots + a'_{2n}x_n = b_2 \\ a''_{33}x_3 + \dots + a''_{3n}x_n = b_3 \\ \dots \\ a''_{r3}x_3 + \dots + a''_{rn}x_n = b_r \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here . There is no need to write the expression of the obtained new coefficients with the previous coefficients. It can be believed that the subjects of the study can easily cope with this task. $r \leq m \leq sa'_{1k}$

In the next step, keeping the first and second equations of this system as they are, using the third equation,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1k-1}x_{k-1} + a_{1k}x_k + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a'_{21}x_1 + a'_{22}x_2 + \dots + a'_{2k-1}x_{k-1} + a'_{2k}x_k + \dots + a'_{2n}x_n = b'_2 \\ \dots \\ a_{k-1k-1}^{(k-2)}x_{k-1} + a_{k-1k}^{(k-2)}x_k + \dots + a_{k-1n}^{(k-2)}x_n = b_{k-1}^{(k-2)} \\ a_{kk}^{(k-1)}x_k + \dots + a_{kn}^{(k-1)}x_n = b_k^{(k-1)} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Here $a_{11} \neq 0, a'_{22} \neq 0, \dots, a_{k-1k-1}^{(k-2)} \neq 0, a_{kk}^{(k-1)} \neq 0, k \leq s$ and . This is a "trapezium-shaped" joint system. However $k \leq n, k < n$ the system is uncertain when In the special case, $k = n$ if so, then

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a'_{22}x_2 + a'_{23}x_3 + \dots + a'_{2n}x_n = b'_2 \\ a''_{33}x_3 + \dots + a''_{3n}x_n = b''_3 \\ \dots \\ a_{nn}^{(n-1)}x_n = b_n^{(n-1)} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

as a "triangular" system is obtained (here). $a_{11} \neq 0, a'_{22} \neq 0, \dots, a_{nn}^{(n-1)} \neq 0$

These systems are equivalent to the given system, and their solution is not difficult for students to master, the solutions found are also the solutions of the given system.[2; 72-76], [5; 122-125].

The above considerations can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The essence of the Gaussian method applied to the solution of the system of linear equations is to bring the given system to either "triangular" or "trapezoidal" ("trapezoidal") systems by carrying out elementary transformations;
- 2) Gauss method can be applied to any system of linear equations; but it is necessary to remember that in the process of successive elimination of unknowns a) if $0=1$ contradictory case appears, the given system is not coherent; b) the system is cooperative if the contradictory case $0=1$ does not occur;
- 3) The joint system becomes a definite system when it is brought to a "triangular" system like (10), and an indefinite system when it is brought to a "trapezoidal" system like (9).

When the basic system is "triangular", the process of finding a solution is clear. If the system is "trapezoidal", then it is possible to solve it as follows. In the system, $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k$ unknowns as "main unknowns" and the remaining unknowns as "free unknowns" from the last equation $x_{k+1}, x_{k+2}, \dots, x_n$ $n - k, x_k$ -we define as dependent on the free unknowns:

starting from the fourth, the unknown from the subsequent equations, and then keeping the first, second, and third equations of the new system the same, and using the fourth equation, the unknown from the subsequent equations, etc. we destroy. x_3, x_4

If a contradiction in the form of $0=1$ is received during conversions, the process is stopped, in this case the system is not convergent; if $0=0$ identity is obtained, we remove it from the system and continue the process. Obviously, this process will not continue indefinitely, and as a result, the following systems are obtained that are equivalent to each other, and therefore equivalent to the given system:

$$x_k = \frac{b_k - a_{k,k+1}x_{k+1} - a_{k,k+2}x_{k+2} - \dots - a_{kn}x_n}{a_{kk}} = \frac{b_k}{a_{kk}} - \frac{a_{k,k+1}}{a_{kk}}x_{k+1} - \frac{a_{k,k+2}}{a_{kk}}x_{k+2} - \dots - \frac{a_{kn}}{a_{kk}}x_n$$

Here, by giving the values of $x_{k+1} = d_{k+1}, x_{k+2} = d_{k+2}, x_{n-1} = d_{n-1}, x_n = d_n$ to the free unknowns x_k , it is suitable for the unknown

$$x_k = \frac{b_k}{a_{kk}} - \frac{a_{k,k+1}}{a_{kk}}d_{k+1} - \frac{a_{k,k+2}}{a_{kk}}d_{k+2} - \dots - \frac{a_{kn}}{a_{kk}}d_n = d_k$$
 we will find the value.

After that, wrote the values we gave to the x_k free unknowns and the corresponding d_k value we calculated for the x_{k-1} main unknown in the second last equation of the system for the main unknown

$$x_{k-1} = \frac{b_{k-1}}{a_{k-1,k-1}} - \frac{a_{k-1,k}}{a_{k-1,k-1}}d_k - \frac{a_{k-1,k+1}}{a_{k-1,k-1}}d_{k+1} - \dots - \frac{a_{k-1,n}}{a_{k-1,k-1}}d_n = d_{k-1}$$
 we will find the price. Continuing with this rule, we can finally calculate the x_1, x_2 values of the system according to the second and first equations and for the $x_2 = d_2, x_1 = d_1$ main unknowns. With this, we find a solution like $d = (d_1; d_2; \dots; d_k; d_{k+1}; \dots; d_n)$ a "trapezoidal" system.

d , since the values assigned to the free unknowns are arbitrary, we cannot talk about the uniqueness of the solution here. Because by assigning any number of different values to the free variables, correspondingly many suitable values for the main variables of the system are found; therefore, in this case, the system has any number of solutions, that is, the system is indeterminate. There are general and special concepts of solutions in uncertain systems.

The solution obtained as a result of solving the uncertain system with respect to the main unknowns and consisting of the expression of the main unknowns with free unknowns is called the general solution of this system. The specific values given to the free variables in the general solution and the values found for the main variables corresponding to them are together the specific solution of the system. It is obvious that any number of specific solutions of the uncertain system can be

Given that here $r \leq s$ we can formulate the following idea:

In a system of homogeneous linear equations, if the number of equations is less than the number of unknowns, this system has any number of non-zero solutions in addition to the zero solution.

Conclusion 2. For the existence of non-zero solutions of a system of n unknown n linear homogeneous equations, it is both necessary and sufficient that its determinant is equal to zero.

Property 1. $\beta = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n)$ and $\gamma = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ vectors are solutions of system (1), then $\beta + \gamma$ vector and $\lambda\beta$ vector are solutions of the system (where λ is any number).

Property 2. Any linear combination of the solutions of a system of homogeneous linear equations is also a solution of the system [3; 160-162],[5; 153-154].

In summarizing the research materials, it is also concluded that introducing students to the system of fundamental solutions of the system of linear homogeneous equations can be considered a useful approach.

As is well known, any linear combination of solutions of a system of homogeneous linear equations is still a solution of the system. Students are told that an interesting problem arises here: is it possible to choose a set of solutions that are not linearly dependent from among the set of solutions of this system, so that all its remaining solutions can be linearly expressed through them?

In response to the question, it is stated that the solutions of a uniform system can be imagined as n -dimensional vectors, and as we know, if the n -number of vectors in the system of n -dimensional vectors is greater than their size ("fitness"), then such a system is linearly dependent. It is clear from here that one can choose a system of solutions that does not depend linearly on the set of solutions of the system of homogeneous equations, so that every remaining solution is a linear combination of this chosen system of solutions. This prompts us to get acquainted with an important concept related to homogeneous systems - the concept of "system of fundamental solutions".

Definition. A maximal linearly independent subset of the set of solutions of a system of linear homogeneous equations is called a system of fundamental solutions.

In other words: The system of solutions forming the basis of the set of solutions of the system of linear homogeneous equations is called the system of fundamental solutions.

Or: A system of fundamental solutions is a linearly independent subset of the set of solutions of a system of linear homogeneous equations such that all other solutions can be linearly expressed by them.

It is obvious that a system of homogeneous linear equations can be called a system of fundamental solutions only if there are non-zero solutions.

It is necessary to pay special attention to one aspect: the same system of homogeneous linear equations has any number of systems of fundamental solutions, but since the systems of vectors forming them constitute a maximal linearly independent system (basis), they are equivalent, so the number of solutions here

must be equal. In short, the number of solutions forming each of them should be the same, even if the system of different fundamental solutions is as many as desired [6-8].

Theorem. In a system of homogeneous linear equations, when the rank r of its matrices is smaller than the n number of unknowns in the system ($r < n$), this system of equations consists $n - r$ solutions to each of the various fundamental solutions of the system [1; 4-5].

Based on this theorem, the method of constructing a system of fundamental solutions becomes clear. So in the given system $r < n$ if it is, they first find its general solution, and then, taking an arbitrary determinant with a non-zero $(n - r)$ composition, consider its line elements as the values of the free unknowns, and find the corresponding special cases. As a result of this process, the number of solutions. $(n - r)$ will be a system of fundamental solutions.

If different from zero another new $(n - r)$ if we choose a structured determinate, again with the same rule $(n - r)$ we find another fundamental system of solutions consisting of a number of solutions.

To evaluate free unknowns, usually $(n - r)$ provided that they are formulated

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{vmatrix} \neq 0$$

they choose the determinant. This is due to the fact that, firstly, the task of calculating the values of the main variables from the general solution becomes much easier when the row elements of this determinant are selected as the value of the free variables, and secondly, it is immediately obvious that this determinant is different from zero.

Scientific-theoretical novelty of the research work: 1) The complete study of the system of linear algebraic equations is "determining whether the given system has a solution, i.e. first, whether it is a joint system", "determining whether it has a unique or multiple solutions", "if the system is joint, all its solutions to find" - it is indicated that it contains the ingredients; 2) In learning and mastering the solution of SLAE Gauss method, Kramer's rule, Comments on the role, advantages and disadvantages of the Kronecker-Capelli criterion are given; 3) The process of learning SLAE is determined by a special "categorical apparatus" and if the student has mastered the essence and functions of the concepts included in the mentioned forms of moral education - "enabling features" at what level, he becomes the subject of solving skills of SLAE in an adequate manner.

The result. 1) The process of mastering the solution of a system of linear algebraic equations involves "determining whether a given system has a solution, i.e., first, whether it is a joint system", "determining whether it has a unique or multiple solutions", "if the system is joint, all its "finding solutions" includes; 2) In learning and mastering the solution of SLAE Gauss method, Kramer's rule, It requires focusing on the role

of the Kronecker-Capelli criterion, its merits and demerits; 3) The study process of SLAE is determined by a special "categorical apparatus" and if the student has mastered the essence and functions of the concepts included among the mentioned forms of spiritual education - "enabling features" at what level, he becomes the subject of SLAE solution skills in an adequate manner.

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